

Table 1: Summary of the collected information from the 17 Scrum-based software projects

ID_Project	Application Domain	Used Technology	Application Type	Project Duration	Team Experience	Amount of risk
P01	Education	.Net	Desktop	3 to 6	4 to 8	9
P02	Enterprise	JavaScript	Web	15 to 18	12 to 15	9
P03	Education	Python	Web	6 to 9	2 to 4	10
P04	Education	Python	Web	9 to 12	8 to 10	8
P05	Management and Business	Java	Desktop	9 to 12	10 to 12	10
P06	Enterprise	PHP	Web	3 to 6	2 to 4	9
P07	Management and Business	PHP	Web	12 to 15	8 to 10	11
P08	Management and Business	JavaScript	Web	6 to 9	4 to 8	9
P09	Enterprise	C++	Embedded	15 to 18	0 to 2	8
P10	Management and Business	Java	IoT	3 to 6	2 to 4	9
P11	[HTML]FFFFFFutilities	Python	Web	12 to 15	10 to 12	9
P12	Enterprise	.Net	Desktop	6 to 9	8 to 10	10
P13	Multimedia	C++	Embedded	9 to 12	0 to 2	10
P14	Hardware	C	Embedded	9 to 12	2 to 4	12
P15	Plugin	json	Web	3 to 6	2 to 4	11
P16	Multimedia	C++	Embedded	6 to 9	4 to 8	12
P17	Multimedia	C++	Embedded	6 to 9	8 to 10	12